

The Impact of Syringe Vibration on Anxiety and Pain in Children During Local Anesthesia Injection

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ABSTRACT

Background : Dental fear and anxiety are the most common reasons that people avoid dental appointments. Fear and anxiety in dental clinics usually result from local anesthesia injections.

Purpose: To evaluate the effect of the vibration-assisted syringe on pain perception in children during different intra-oral injections of local anesthesia, as well as, assessment of anxiety expressed by children receiving different intra-oral injections using vibration-assisted syringe.

Methods and Materials: This study was conducted as a prospective randomized controlled clinical trial. A total number of 120 children aged 4-8 years was selected from patients visiting the pediatric dental clinic at Mansoura University. The children were assigned into four equal groups (30 children each) according to the type of intra-oral injection needed for their treatment; Group I: children underwent upper posterior buccal infiltration, Group II: children underwent inferior alveolar nerve block, Group III: children underwent upper anterior infiltration, and Group IV: children underwent posterior palatal infiltration. This study was conducted considering the split mouth design. Each child was subjected to both anesthetic injections; the conventional and the vibration-assisted in two separate dental visits with two weeks apart was established between the two visits. The order of administration of local anesthesia whether vibration-assisted or conventional was randomly determined. The site of administration (right or left) was determined according to the child 's chief complaint. Immediately following the administration, pain perceived was assessed using Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) while the anxiety was assessed using Faces Anxiety Scale (FAS).

Results : On comparing the difference in pain perception by VAS, it was significantly lower in Vibraject-assisted injections in groups I, III, and IV (p value = 0.034; 0.014 and 0.000 respectively). On comparing the difference in anxiety by FAS, it was significantly lower in Vibraject-assisted injections only in group IV subjects (p value = 0.016).

Conclusions: On the light of this study, Vibraject provides less pain in comparison to conventional injection. Some of the children were less anxious when injected by Vibraject-assisted syringe in comparison to the conventional syringe. Vibraject may be a promising method of delivering local anesthesia in children. However, further research is needed to confirm the efficacy of Vibraject in providing less painful dental local anesthesia in children.

KEYWORDS: Dental anesthesia; Vibraject; Vibration; Vibration-assisted anesthesia; Visual analogue scale; Faces anxiety scale; Pain; Anxiety

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INTRODUCTION

Dental fear and anxiety are the most common reasons that people avoid dental appointments.¹ Children who perceive significant pain during dental procedures usually exhibit greater behavior problems at subsequent visits, resulting in more need for restraint and longer procedures. Also, the children who experience discomfort may avoid necessary dental care and become more likely to avoid future care as adults.²

Fear and anxiety in dental clinics usually result from local anesthesia injections.³ The main purpose of local anesthesia is to eliminate pain in a particular area but the actual method of delivering the anesthetic drug is proven to be anxiety provoking and painful because of the stimulation produced by the needle insertion and injection of the anesthetic solution.⁴

Pain control is considered a cornerstone which affects the behavior in a pediatric dental clinic. Furthermore, effective pain control at the time of local dental injections is crucial to accomplishing child's comfort, cooperation, and compliance which coincide with the modern dental care.⁵

Dentist proposed several methods in order to reduce the pain associated with local anesthetic injections such as topical analgesics application,⁶ distraction techniques,⁷ application of counterirritation,⁸ buffering and warming the local anesthetic solutions,⁹ gradual anesthetic injections,¹⁰ the use of enhanced syringes with fine needles, and injection site precooling¹¹.

Although, these techniques have been reported in many studies, however, there is no conclusive painless injection technique has been established. Vibratory stimulation is one of the several nonpharmacological techniques used to reduce pain associated with local anesthetic injection. The idea of vibration is based on the gate control theory, by

acting as counter stimulation on to the site of injection thereby alleviating pain.¹²

In 1965, Melzack and Wall introduced the "Gate Control" theory which improves the understanding of the pain transmission. The theory suggests that the reduction of pain experienced can be achieved by application non-noxious stimuli (like using appropriate pressure or vibration).¹³ Furthermore, it claims that the stimulation of nerve fibers with larger diameter by non-noxious stimuli can reduce the perception of pain.¹⁴

In the clinical practice while working in the very sensitive oral cavity where more than a third of the brain somatosensory cortex is devoted to sensory inputs from the oral cavity. Vibration stimuli are easily applied in the orofacial areas in order to raise the pain threshold, to relieve the pain of dental origin, to manage chronic intractable orofacial pain, and acute or chronic musculoskeletal pain.¹⁵

Lundeberg et al. reported a reduction of pain during vibratory stimulation in patients suffering acute or chronic musculoskeletal pain of different organs. Also, a study investigated the effect of the vibration on pain during local anesthesia injections found that, compared to conventional injections, injections with vibration resulted in less pain and lower pain rating.¹⁶

Lately, several studies were done to investigate the effect of vibration on pain during local anesthesia injections but the results are equivocal. Vibraject is a small, vibratory, battery operated device which has an attachment that snaps on to the standard dental syringe producing vibrations at high frequency on to the needle to block pain sensation during local anesthetic injections.¹⁷ If effective, this device may represent a time-efficient, non-pharmacological technique to improve the experience of children receiving local anesthetic during dental procedures.¹⁸

Therefore, the purpose of this study was to evaluate the effect of vibration using Vibraject on both pain and anxiety in children.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design

The child's recruitment process was started from January 2015 until January 2017. This study was conducted as a prospective randomized controlled trial. The study was approved by the Mansoura Research Ethics Committee, Faculty of Dentistry, Mansoura University in concordance with the Helsinki Declaration Principals.

Subjects

A total number of 120 consecutive child aged 4-8 years was recruited from the children visiting the pediatric dental clinic, Faculty of Dentistry, Mansoura University for this study. The children were assigned into four equal groups (30 children each) according to the site of intra-oral injection needed for their treatment; as follows:

Group I: children underwent upper posterior buccal infiltration.

Group II: children underwent inferior alveolar nerve block.

Group III: children underwent upper anterior infiltration.

Group IV: children underwent posterior palatal infiltration.

Inclusions and exclusions criteria

Medically fit children with an existence of required bilateral mandibular, maxillary or upper anterior segment ordinary dental treatment which needs local anesthesia administration were recruited for this study. All child should have had a positive or a definitely positive behavior according to the Frankel Scale. While we excluded those children suffering from medical illness, neurosensory

disturbances, psychiatric disorders, or those who could not comprehend the pain measures. Emergencies and acute dental conditions also were exclusion criteria.

Pre-anesthetic procedures

The preoperative behavioral assessment was done using Frankel Scale (which separate observed behaviors into 4 categories ranging from definitely negative to definitely positive).¹⁹ A signed informed consent was obtained from the parents or the guardian of every child after a brief explanation of the procedures, as well as, highlighting the possible future publication. The child was instructed to sit on the dental chair comfortably and confidence was gained before examination and dental and medical history taking.

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TSD "tell show do" technique was used for behavior modification for all children. A simple explanation of the technique of the administration of local anesthesia was given to the child. The dialogue for both of the two techniques was standardized as follows: "Now it is time for your gum and tooth to go to sleep, I have a magic strawberry gel (referring to the topical anesthetic) for your gum and a sleepy pen (referring to the syringe barrel without the needle) for your tooth. I will place the magic strawberry gel on a cotton pad and swipe your gum with it and I will place the sleepy pen adjacent to

your tooth so that the sleepy juice inside it can get out and make your tooth go to sleep.

Anesthetic technique designing

This study was conducted considering the splitmouth design. Each child was subjected to both anesthetic injections; the conventional injections and the vibration-assisted injections in two separate dental visits. One to two weeks' interval was established between the two visits. The order of administration of local anesthesia whether vibration assisted or conventional was randomly determined.

To determine if the vibratory device (Vibraject; Vibraject® MiltextInc LLC., York, PA, USA) was used or not for the first visit the operator selected one of two cards with either the letter V or C printed on (denoting vibration assisted or conventional) from an opaque bag. While to determine the first side (right or left) to be injected we considered the child chief complaint. All children had received local anesthesia and completed their treatment by the same operator.

Injection technique

Topical anesthetic gel (20% benzocaine) was used for all children before local anesthesia administration. It was applied for 1–2 min on previously dried mucosal surface before both anesthesia techniques. For every child using either of the two injections, the same amount of the local anesthesia (Mepivacaine hydrochloride 2%, with Levonordefrin 1/20,000) was injected slowly considering the anatomical landmarks. Immediately following the administration, the pain and the anxiety were evaluated.

The purpose of the study

The primary outcome was the evaluation of the effect of the vibration-assisted syringe on pain perception in children during different intraoral injections of local anesthesia, as well as the

assessment of anxiety expressed by children receiving different intra-oral injections using the vibration-assisted syringe.

Pain measuring tool used in this study

The Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) which is a measurement instrument for the amount of pain that a patient feels ranging across a continuum from none to an extreme amount of pain. Practically, the VAS is usually a horizontal line, 100 mm in length, anchored by word descriptor at each end, no pain and worst pain ever.²⁰ After simple explanation each child was asked to rate the actual pain he/she felt during local anesthesia administration using the VAS. The child was asked to mark on the scale line at the point that he/she felt it represented his/her degree of pain. The VAS score was determined by measuring in millimeters from the left-hand end of the line to the point that the child marks.

Anxiety measuring tool used in this study

The Faces Anxiety Scale (FAS) which is one item faces scale with drawings of five faces expressing increasing levels of anxiety. The left most face is not scared at all, the next one is a little bit more scared and right up to the most scared possible (right most face).²¹ Using FAS, the child was asked to choose one of the five faces that shows how much anxiety he or she felt at the administration time.

Variables studied and statistical analysis

Based on a power analysis and sample size calculation, we estimated that a minimum of 30 subjects should be recruited for each group. The site of injection, the type of injection whether infiltration or inferior nerve block (IDB), the pain score, and the anxiety score all were recorded for each child. Data were analyzed by the SPSS statistical package version 20 (SPSS, Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). The quantitative data were expressed as a median and range after test the normality using KolmogorovSmirnov test.

Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to compare the difference in either VAS or FAS on using the conventional versus Vibraject-assisted injection within the same patient in the four studied groups. P value is considered significant when ≤ 0.05 .

The correlation between pain (VAS) score and age of studied subjects was analyzed by the Pearson correlation, while the correlation between anxiety

Fig. (1) The Vibraject attached to the conventional aspirating syringe

(FAS) score and age of studied subjects was analyzed by the Spearman correlation. The results were interpreted as follow; p value ≤ 0.01 or 0.05 (mentioned in specified tables) is considered significant. The correlation was said to be no correlation, positive correlation, and negative correlation when $r=0$, $r=1$, and $r=-1$ respectively. The strength of the correlation was said to be strong,

Fig. (2) Vibraject-assisted injection followed by the conventional injection in the same child in two subsequent visits

moderate, weak, and very weak correlation when $r = -1.0$ to -0.5 or 1.0 to 0.5 , $r = -0.5$ to -0.3 or 0.3 to 0.5 , $r = -0.3$ to -0.1 or 0.1 to 0.3 , and $r = -0.1$ to 0.1 respectively.

RESULTS

Children characteristics

One-hundred-forty-seven consecutive children existence of required bilateral dental procedures were recruited in the study, however, 27 children were excluded as they missed the second visit or showed negative or definitely negative behavior according to Frankel Scale on the second visit. Finally, 120 children were included in the analysis, of them, 66 were boys and 54 girls. The median age was 7 years (range; 4-8 years). The children were divided into four equal groups according to the site of intra-oral anesthetic injection required for their treatment. Each child received two different local anesthetic injections (conventional and vibrationassisted) in two subsequent visits with a total number of 240 injections.

Pain measurement

The median (range) value of VAS on using the conventional syringe was 4.1 (0.7-10) in group I (UPI) subjects; 4.550 (0.5-10) in Group II (IANB) subjects; 6.700 (2.8-10) in group III (UAI) subjects and 6.600 (3.3-8.4) in group IV (PPI) subjects as shown in **table 1**.

Meanwhile, the median (range) value of VAS on using Vibraject-assisted syringe was 2.900 (0-10) in group I (UPI) subjects; 2.900 (0-9.2) in group II (IANB) subjects; 5.650 (1.7-10) in group III (UAI) subjects and 6.000 (1.8-8.6) in group IV (PPI) subjects as shown in **table 1**.

On comparing the difference in VAS on using the conventional syringe and the Vibraject-assisted syringe, a significant difference was detected in both groups I, III and IV (p value = 0.034; 0.014 and 0.000 respectively) with VAS is higher on using conventional syringe than the Vibrajectassisted syringe. While the insignificant difference was detected in group II subjects (p value = 0.245) (**Table 1**).

TABLE (1) Comparison of the VAS between the four studied groups.

	VAS (0-10)		
	Conventional injection; median (range) VAS	Vibraject-assisted injection; median (range) VAS	P value*
Group I (UPI)	4.100 (0.7-10)	2.900 (0-10)	0.034**
Group II (IANB)	4.550 (0.5-10)	2.900 (0-9.2)	0.245
Group III (UAI)	6.700 (2.8-10)	5.650 (1.7-10)	0.014**
Group IV (PPI)	6.600 (3.3-8.4)	6.000 (1.8-8.6)	0.000**

* *Wilcoxon signed-rank test.*

** *is significant (P value < 0.05 is significant).*

Anxiety measurement

The median (range) value of FAS on using conventional syringe was 3 (1-5) in group I (UPI) subjects; 3 (1-5) in Group II (IANB) subjects; 4 (25) in group III (UAI) subjects and 4 (1-5) in group IV (PPI) subjects as shown in **table 2**.

Meanwhile, the median (range) value of FAS on using Vibraject-assisted syringe was 3 (1-5) in group I (UPI) subjects; 3 (1-5) in Group II (IANB) subjects; 3 (1-5) in group III (UAI) subjects and 3 (1-5) in group IV (PPI) subjects as shown in **table 2**.

On comparing the difference in FAS on using the conventional syringe and the Vibraject-assisted syringe, a significant difference was detected in only group IV subjects (p value = 0.016) with FAS is higher on using conventional syringe than the Vibraject-assisted syringe. While the insignificant difference was detected between group I, II, III and IV (p value = 0.6, 0.325 and 0.316 respectively) (**table 2**).

TABLE (2) Comparison of the FAS between the four studied groups.

	FAS (1-5)		
	Conventional injection; median (range) FAS	Vibraject-assisted injection; median (range) FAS	P value *
Group I (UPI)	3.00 (1-5)	3.00 (1-5)	0.060
Group II (IANB)	3.00 (1-5)	3.00 (1-5)	0.325
Group III (UAI)	4.00 (2-5)	3.00 (1-5)	0.310
Group IV (PPI)	4.00 (1-5)	3.00 (1-5)	0.016 **

* Wilcoxon signed-rank test.

** is significant (P value < 0.05 is significant).

Age correlation

The age median (range) value in the four studied groups was 6.5 (4-8) years in group I subjects; 5.5 (4-8) years in group II subjects; 7 (4-8) years in group III subjects and 8 (6-8) in group IV subjects.

Correlation between pain (VAS) and subjects' age

On correlating the VAS value and age on using Vibraject-assisted syringe as illustrated in **table 3**, significant strong negative correlation was found in group I subjects ($r=-0.756$; $p= 0.000$); significant strong negative correlation was found in group II subjects ($r= -0.692$; $p=0.000$); significant moderate negative correlation was found in group III subjects ($r= -0.419$; $p= 0.021$) and insignificant moderate negative correlation was found in group IV subjects ($r=-0.329$; $p= 0.076$).

TABLE (3) Correlation between VAS and age in the four studied groups using Pearson correlation for Vibraject-assisted injection.

	Age (Median) years	VAS (Median)	r	p
Group I (UPI)	6.5 (4-8)	3.00 (1-5)	-0.664 a	0.000*
Group II (IANB)	5.5 (4-8)	3.00 (1-5)	-0.584a	0.001*
Group III (UAI)	7 (4-8)	3.00 (1-5)	-0.270	0.149
Group IV (PPI)	8 (6-8)	3.00 (1-5)	-0.413b	0.023*

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Group III (UAI)	7 (4-8)	5.650 (1.7-10)	-0.419b	0.021*
Group IV (PPI)	8 (6-8)	6.000 (1.8-8.6)	-0.329	0.076
Level of significance				
a. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				
b. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).				

Correlation between anxiety (FAS) and subjects' age

On correlating the FAS value and age on using Vibraject-assisted syringe as illustrated in **table 4**, significant strong negative correlation was found in group I subjects ($r= -0.664$; $p= 0.000$); significant strong negative correlation was found in group II subjects ($r= -0.584$; $p=0.000$); insignificant weak negative correlation was found in group III subjects ($r= -0.270$; $p= 0.149$) and significant moderate negative correlation was found in group IV subjects ($r=-0.413$; $p= 0.023$).

TABLE (4) Correlation between FAS and age in the four studied groups using Spearman correlation for Vibraject-assisted injection.

	Age (Median) Years	FAS (Median)	r	p
Group I (UPI)	6.5 (4-8)	3.00 (1-5)	-0.664 a	0.000*
Group II (IANB)	5.5 (4-8)	3.00 (1-5)	-0.584a	0.001*
Group III (UAI)	7 (4-8)	3.00 (1-5)	-0.270	0.149
Group IV (PPI)	8 (6-8)	3.00 (1-5)	-0.413b	0.023*
Level of significance				
a. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				
b. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).				

DISCUSSION

The age limit of the study ranged from 4-8 years as it is the most frequent age range of children

attending to the Mansoura University dental pediatric clinic. Also, this age range was suitable for explaining the pain and anxiety scales to the children and obtaining reliable scores from them.

In this study, all local anesthetic injections were administered by the same dentist in order to control operator-related variables such as gender, technical expertise, and previous experience.

The 27-gauge needle was chosen for all dental injections to simplify the protocol because this needle size is commonly used by providers in a typical dental practice. Also, clinical studies have demonstrated that there is no difference in perceived pain between 30-gauge (small gauge), 27-gauge (medium gauge), and 25-gauge (large gauge) needles.²²

As a routine, prior to every local anesthetic injection, topical anesthetic was applied according to the protocol of local anesthetic injections in Mansoura University dental pediatric clinic in concordance with ethical committee approval.

To the best of our knowledge, other studies investigating the Vibraject in children conducted their studies regardless the injection site which gave us the advantage of evaluating pain perceived during injection with and without vibration in four different injecting sites (IANB, UPI, UAI, PPI) in children.

In the present study, children evaluated their pain using VAS which was found to be easily explained by the dentist and understood by children. Also, the children rated their anxiety using FAS which was appropriate for their ages to select the face they felt most like at that moment. Both scales were found to be time- saving as they took very short time to be administered and for a score to be obtained.

Vibraject was chosen in this study as the vibration-providing device as it is a simple battery operated-device, easy to be clipped to the syringe and requires little if any change from the normal injection technique. Also, it is relatively inexpensive

in comparison to other vibratory devices (e.g dental vibrate).

The results of our study revealed that the use of Vibraject-assisted syringe has a significant reduction in the perceived pain in children in group I, group III, and group IV, while in group II the reduction in perceived pain did not reach a significant level. Also, the results showed that the use of the Vibraject-assisted syringe has significantly decreased anxiety in group IV children, while the insignificant difference was detected in group I, group II, and group III.

This result was in accordance with Chaudhry et al.²³ who also evaluated the efficacy of Vibraject in decreasing pain during local anesthetic injection in children. Also, Chandrasekaran et al.²⁴ stated that Vibraject has significantly reduced pain during delivery of local anesthesia in adults. Furthermore, Terrett et al.²⁵ concluded that Vibraject is effective in decreasing perceived pain levels during dental injections. They included 329 adult participants in their study.

In a study conducted by Quarnstrom et al.²⁶, they compared the Wand to Vibraject and found no difference in injection discomfort between the two systems. Although they concluded that both the Wand and Vibraject were effective and recommended using them to decrease dental injection pain perception, the authors did not compare the devices to the traditional dental syringe technique.

On the other hand, Saijo et al.¹⁸ conducted a single-blind randomized controlled study among 10 adult volunteers and found that Vibraject did not provide any benefits over the conventional local anesthetic injection. The possible explanation for the difference between their results and the results of this study is that they included only ten participants which represent a very small sample size that does not permit adequate statistical analysis to determine differences between the test and control groups.

They also divided their participants into two groups (5 each) so that one group is considered the test group and the other group is considered the control group, while in this study each child served as his own control as there are variations in perceiving pain from one person to another. In addition, the volume of anesthetic solution administered in Saijo's study (0.1 ml) did not represent a dose typically used for dental treatment.

Another single-blind randomized controlled study was done by Roeber et al.²⁷ among children. They also were in disagreement with our results. The possible explanation for this disagreement is that Roeber et al.²⁷ did not compare a Vibraject-assisted injection and a conventional injection within the same patient.

Unfortunately, there is no publication regarding the effect of Vibraject on anxiety levels. However, in a study evaluating the effect of vibration, using a vibration producing device other than Vibraject (Dental vibrate), on pain and anxiety in adults during local anesthesia administration, they concluded that anxiety levels were significantly lower in the vibration group than in the conventional anesthesia group.¹

Further findings from our study, is that we noticed a significant negative correlation between pain (VAS) and children's age when using the Vibraject-assisted syringe, in group I, group II and group III. While in group IV, there was a moderate negative correlation that didn't reach a significant level. This correlation might explain why there was no significant difference between VAS scores on using the conventional syringe and Vibraject-assisted syringe in group II. The group II has the lowest age median 6.5 (4-8) years between the four groups of our study.

Another potentially possible explanation for the insignificant effect of using Vibraject in this group is that the VAS for pain self-report has not been

validated for use in children younger than five years old, and group II included many 4 years old children.²⁷

Moreover, another significant negative correlation was found in our study between anxiety (FAS) and children's age when using the Vibraject-assisted injection in group I, group II and group IV. While in group III, there was a weak negative correlation that did not reach a significant level.

In the present study, we observed that the older the child the more acceptance, less pain and less anxiety he/she shows towards the Vibraject-assisted syringe. This may be due to the voice and the sensation of vibration produced by Vibraject that may be scary for younger children.

Unfortunately, there were no other studies found in literature mentioning these correlations, keeping in mind that published studies evaluating the effect of Vibraject on pain and anxiety levels are very few and only two of them are conducted among children.

CONCLUSION

Vibraject may be a promising method for alleviating pain during local dental anesthetic injections in children. Vibraject is effective in reducing pain perceived during local anesthetic injections in comparison to the conventional injection technique in clinical dental procedures in 4-8 years' children. Regarding anxiety, some of the children were less anxious when injected using Vibraject in comparison to the conventional injections. The efficacy, the acceptance, and the tolerability of Vibraject increased with the increase in children's age. Further research is needed to confirm these results.

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